

Analytical Applications of the Formation of Basic Beryllium Complex Carbonates

Apurba Kumar Sengupta

Based on the formation of characteristic and insoluble crystals of hexammine-cobalt (III) beryllcarbonate $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]_2(\text{Be}_4\text{O}(\text{CO}_3)_6) \cdot 11\text{H}_2\text{O}$, rapid acidimetric and gravimetric methods for estimating beryllium, singly or in presence of other cations, have been suggested.

From beryllium salt solutions in excess of alkali metal bicarbonates and ammonium carbonate, the present author has been able to isolate^{1,2} salts of the complex anion, $[\text{Be}_4\text{O}(\text{CO}_3)_6]^{6-}$. It has also been found that the insoluble hexammine cobalt (III) salt of the above anion has two hydrates, having three well-defined crystalline modifications, best described as needles, tetrahedra, and polyhedra. Earlier, Pirtea and co-workers³ reported precipitation of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6][(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{Be}_2(\text{CO}_3)_2(\text{OH})_3] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ from the above beryllium solutions and suggested a gravimetric method for estimating beryllium.

In investigating the possibility of a microscopic test by adding $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CO}_3$ solution (10%) and hexammine-cobalt(III) chloride solution (2%) to beryllium salt solutions, we found it a very sensitive one, detecting Be up to 0.14 γ (by the appearance of tetrahedra or needles). But unfortunately, the test has been found to be inapplicable in presence of many other cations. It has also been found by the present author² that the hexammine-cobalt (III) berylli carbonate dissolves in acids according to the following reaction:

Based on this reaction, an acidimetric method for estimating beryllium has been suggested, in which the difficulty arising sometimes in the gravimetric method from the precipitation of the different hydrates of the hexammine-cobalt (III) salt has been completely removed.

In suggesting the gravimetric method, which requires almost the same time as the acidimetric one, we have discussed along with others the interferences arising from the presence of excess amounts of ammonium salts and of EDTA, which were not mentioned by Pirtea *et al.*³ In contrary to their observation, some what dilution of the test solutions has been found to help in the complete precipitation of beryllium and also in obtaining a homogeneous precipitate. Incidentally, the factor in calculating the amount of beryllium from

1. Sengupta, *Science & Culture*, 1960, 25, 426.

2. *Idem*, *J. Inorg Nucl. Chem.* (In press).

3. *Revista de chemie* (Bucharest), 1956, 7, 427; *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1958, 159, 205; 1959, 165, 183.

the weighed amount of precipitate is 0.03863 and it is different from that recorded by Pirtea *et al.*³.

EXPERIMENTAL

Acidimetric Determination of Beryllium.—Sodium fluoride solution (2.5%) used in the method was prepared from a reagent grade sodium fluoride which was heated at *ca.* 900° for several hours in a platinum dish. It was powdered and then dissolved in water. The solution was filtered, made neutral to phenolphthalein indicator, and preserved in a polythene bottle. A standard beryllium nitrate solution was prepared by dissolving recrystallised and sublimed basic beryllium acetate⁴ in redistilled reagent quality nitric acid. The strength of the beryllium solution was checked by estimating Be as BeO in the usual way.

The beryllium solution (50 ml, containing 14.14 mg. Be) was neutralised by sodium bicarbonate to the appearance of a faint precipitate and it was then just dissolved by adding a dilute acid. An excess of ammonium carbonate (3 g.) solution (25 ml) was then added. The mixture was stirred in order to redissolve the precipitate formed completely and gently warmed, when found necessary, in order to facilitate the process. The solution was cooled to the room temperature, diluted to 200 ml, and immediately an excess of hexamine-cobalt (III) chloride solution was added with stirring. Precipitation usually occurred immediately, but required a few minutes' stirring when the amount of the carbonate was in large excess with respect to beryllium. After allowing it to stand for about 40 min., the solution was filtered through No. 40 filter paper. The precipitate was washed with water till free of ammonia and other salts. The filter paper was transferred to the original beaker and an excess of a standard H₂SO₄ solution (*N*/10 or *N*/20 depending on the amount of beryllium) was then added. The solution was boiled for about 10 min. in order to remove CO₂ completely. It was cooled to the room temperature, transferred to a colorless, transparent plastic beaker, and an excess of the sodium fluoride solution was added to it. The excess of acid was then back-titrated against phenolphthalein indicator by a standard NaOH solution (*N*/10 or *N*/20) to the appearance of a pink tint in the orange solution. The amount of beryllium was then calculated from equation (1), where 3.5 ml of (*N*) H₂SO₄ ≡ 9 mg. of Be.

The results are recorded in Table I. A few experiments were carried out utilising sodium bicarbonate instead of ammonium carbonate.

TABLE I

Be taken.	(NH ₄) ₂ CO ₃ .	NaHCO ₃ .	NaF.	Be found.	Error.
14.0 ₀₀ mg.	6.0 g.		2.00 g.	14.030 mg.	-0.050 mg.
14.080	3.0		2.00	14.140	+0.060
14.080	3.0		1.00	14.050	-0.030
14.080	2.0		2.00	14.080	±0.000
8.060	2.0		1.00	7.980	-0.080
7.040	3.0		2.00	7.070	+0.030
4.224	3.0		0.63	4.202	-0.022
4.030	2.0		1.00	3.974	-0.056
1.408	3.0		0.63	1.396	-0.012
14.080	..	3.0 g.	1.30	14.130	+0.050
1.408	:	3.0	0.63	1.410	+0.002

Gravimetric Determination of Beryllium.—The gravimetric determination of beryllium as its hexammine-cobalt (III) beryllcarbonate, $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6][\text{Be}_4\text{O}(\text{CO}_3)_6]$ aq, has become complicated by the existence of its two hydrates, viz., with 10 and 11 H_2O . From microscopic examination of the precipitates, it was found, however, that from solutions containing 2.5% $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CO}_3$ only the 11-hydrate crystallised when the concentration of beryllium in total volume of the solution ranged from 2.287 mg. to 18.29 mg. of Be. With higher ammonium carbonate concentrations, e.g. 5% $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CO}_3$, the 10-hydrate was precipitated from solutions containing 2.287 mg. of Be, but with greater amounts of beryllium, the 11-hydrate crystallised from such solutions.

From a beryllium solution containing 2.287 to 18.29 mg. of Be, the hexammine-cobalt(III) beryllcarbonate 11-hydrate was precipitated as before (*vide supra*). The solution was filtered through a No. 4 sintered glass crucible. The precipitate was first washed with water till free of other salts and then thrice with dry acetone. Air was then drawn in for half an hour; the crucible was left for 15 min. in air and weighed. The results are shown in Table II. The amounts of beryllium were calculated by assuming the precipitate to have the formula $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]_2[\text{Be}_4\text{O}(\text{CO}_3)_6] \cdot 11\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

TABLE II

Be taken.	Wt. of ppt.	Be found.	Error.
18.290 mg.	0.4733 g.	18.320 mg.	+0.030 mg.
16.680	0.4318	16.680	±0.000
9.146	0.2367	9.143	-0.003
8.340	0.2155	8.324	-0.016
4.573	0.1175	4.539	-0.034
2.287	0.0590	2.279	-0.008

Interferences.—It has been pointed out above that a very high concentration of ammonium carbonate interferes. The other ammonium salts also, if present in large amounts, were found to have a considerable influence on the nature of the precipitate and on its complete precipitation. Thus, it was found that from a solution containing 4.573 mg. Be and 2% with respect to ammonium nitrate, the beryllcarbonate was precipitated completely; but with higher concentrations of ammonium nitrate, the precipitation occurred after a long time and sometimes even after keeping overnight, the precipitation was not complete. EDTA was also found to have a similar effect (*vide* Table III). The usual anions, viz., nitrate, chloride, or sulphate, did not interfere. But, besides the alkali metals, others interfere by precipitation of their hydroxides, carbonates, etc.

TABLE III

Effect of EDTA on the precipitation of the complex carbonate.

Be = 4.573 mg. $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CO}_3$ added = 2.5 g. Total volume of the solution at the time of precipitation = 115 ml., except in the last experiment, where it was 200 ml.

$\text{Na}_2\text{-EDTA}$ (10%).	Be found*	Error.
0 ml	4.539 mg.	-0.034 mg.
5	4.539	-0.034
8	4.504	-0.069
10	4.442	-0.131
30	4.064	-0.509
10	4.466	-0.105

*Calculated by supposing the precipitates to be the 11-hydrates of the complex carbonate.

Determination of Beryllium in presence of other Cations.—Beryllium can, however, be estimated in presence of many other cations by adding EDTA in order to mask them⁵, but it is necessary to keep the amounts of EDTA and ammonium salts within the minimum, as has been described above.

To the beryllium solution, after adding 8ml of Na₂-EDTA (10%), solid NaHCO₃ was added till the pH of the solution was raised to 7.0 (approx.). Sodium bicarbonate (3 g.) was added to the solution (50-100ml), stirred, warmed for a minute or two till a clear solution was obtained. It was then cooled and diluted to 200 ml. An excess of hexamine-cobalt (III) chloride solution was added with stirring. After allowing it to stand for an hour, it was filtered, washed, and dried as before. The results are recorded in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Be taken = 4.573mg. NaHCO₃ added = 3g. The determined values for Be was calculated by assuming the precipitates to be the 11-hydrate of the complex carbonate.

Metals present.	Na ₂ -EDTA (10%).	Be found.	Error.
Ni ²⁺ 5.0 mg.	8 ml.	4.535 mg.	-0.038 mg.
" 50.0	8	4.551	-0.022
Cu ²⁺ 5.0	5	4.565	-0.008
" 50.0	5	4.569	-0.004
Zn ²⁺ 5.0	8	4.535	-0.038
" 50.0	10	4.562	-0.011
Ni ²⁺ Cu ²⁺ & Zn ²⁺ 5.45 & 45 (respectively).	8	4.565	-0.008
Mg ²⁺ 5	8	4.554	-0.019
" 50	8	4.565	-0.008
Ca ²⁺ 5	8	4.548	-0.027
" 50	8	4.569	+0.004
Al ³⁺ 50	8	4.565	+0.012
Fe ³⁺ 50	8	4.539	-0.034
Al ³⁺ & Fe ³⁺ 35 & 25	8	4.571	-0.002

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CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
KALYANI UNIVERSITY,
KALYANI, W. BENGAL.

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